

Policy

on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in the Educational Process Berdyansk State Pedagogical University

Approved by the Academic Council of Berdyansk State Pedagogical University,
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Preamble

Artificial intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into the educational environment, transforming approaches to learning, teaching, and assessment. Its application opens new opportunities for both educators and learners – from information retrieval and structuring, and support of language and communication skills, to learning analytics and the creation of new forms of educational content. At the same time, AI use is accompanied by a number of challenges, including risks to academic integrity, assessment validity, data protection, intellectual property rights, and equity of access.

Particular attention must be given to generative artificial intelligence (GenAI), which creates new content – text, images, code, multimedia. In this document, the term GenAI refers to systems capable of generating and transforming content (e.g., ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini, DeepSeek), while AI refers to the broader spectrum of technologies applied in education and research.

Berdyansk State Pedagogical University, as an institution providing education at all levels of higher education and actively integrating into the European and global educational space, recognizes the need to regulate practices related to the use of AI in the educational process. This Policy is aimed at achieving a balance between the innovative potential of new technologies and the preservation of fundamental academic values: accountability, transparency, integrity, equity of opportunity for all learners, and trust in learning outcomes.

The use of AI tools for assessment or access to education falls under heightened legal requirements of the EU (Annex III of the AI Act). The University complies with the relevant procedures and uses only tools whose providers meet conformity requirements.

This document establishes the principles, rules, and mechanisms to be followed by students, faculty, and administrative staff of the University in the use of AI for learning, teaching, and assessment. It is based on international approaches to the responsible use of digital technologies, as well as the principles of academic integrity, inclusiveness, and open science.

The provisions are of a framework nature and serve as the foundation for the development of more detailed instructions, guidelines, and procedures at the level of individual programs and university units.

1 General Provisions

1.1. Purpose. To establish rules for the responsible use of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) in the educational process in order to safeguard assessment validity, academic integrity, data confidentiality, and to promote AI literacy among students and faculty.

1.2. Scope. This Policy applies to all levels of education, all forms and modes of learning (on-campus, blended, distance), and all participants in the educational process (students, instructors, program guarantors, etc.).

1.3. Basic Principle. Responsible use of GenAI in learning is permitted by default, unless otherwise explicitly restricted by the instructor for a specific assignment or part thereof, when performed in a controlled environment to preserve assessment validity.

1.4. Principles of Application

- **Accountability of the work's author.** Responsibility for the content and quality of created materials always rests with the student or instructor who delegated tasks to GenAI; GenAI itself cannot be considered an author or co-author.
- **Transparency.** Each instance of GenAI use must be disclosed in a standardized form, indicating the tools, versions, dates, and tasks for which they were applied.
- **Validity and fairness of assessment.** Assignments and assessment formats must be designed to ensure that results reflect the actual knowledge and skills of students, even when AI is used, and guarantee equal conditions for all participants in the educational process.
- **Confidentiality and data security.** The use of AI must not violate personal data protection rules, intellectual property rights, or the University's internal policies.
- **Inclusiveness and accessibility.** AI may be used as a support tool for students with special educational needs, ensuring equal access to learning.

2 Regulatory Foundations

This Policy has been developed in consideration of international and national frameworks on AI ethics, data protection, academic integrity, and educational quality, including: UNESCO Recommendation on the Ethics of AI (2021), GDPR (EU Regulation 2016/679), the European AI Act, UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (2021), the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA), and the Laws of Ukraine On Education, On Higher Education, and On the Protection of Personal Data.

3 Policy Position and Application of GenAI in Learning

3.1. Policy Position. Responsible use of GenAI in the educational process is permitted, except in cases where the instructor explicitly prohibits its use for the entire assignment or a part of it and requires completion in a controlled environment (e.g., exams, verification of basic competencies, accreditation requirements).

3.2. Syllabus and Assignment Specification. Instructors are encouraged to specify the permitted mode of GenAI use in course syllabi and in assignment instructions: “permitted,” “permitted with restrictions” (with a list of allowed purposes), or “prohibited in a controlled environment.” In the absence of such an indication, the default mode is “responsible use permitted.”

3.3. Transparency of Use. In all extracurricular written works and projects where GenAI is applied, disclosure of AI contributions is recommended. The University recommends using the GAIDeT standard (tool/version/date; delegated tasks).

3.4. Grounds for Restrictions. Temporary or targeted prohibitions are only allowed to preserve assessment validity, ensure verification of key individual competencies, protect confidentiality and intellectual property, meet accreditation requirements, or where the nature of the assignment objectively requires it.

3.5. Assistive Technologies and Inclusion. The use of GenAI as part of reasonable accommodations for students with special educational needs (SEN) is permitted under University policies, provided confidentiality requirements are met.

3.6. Reciprocity and Trust. If an instructor uses GenAI for formative feedback or for creating learning materials, this must be transparently communicated to students.

4 Roles and Responsibilities

4.1. Program Guarantors and Quality Assurance Teams: coordinate the position on GenAI at the program level; review learning outcomes, teaching methods, and assessment practices in line with this Policy; ensure consistency of approaches across disciplines.

4.2. Instructors: define the mode of GenAI use in syllabi and assignments; ensure assessment validity; verify AI-use disclosures in student work via the GAIDeT Declaration Generator; comply with confidentiality requirements; explain rules for GenAI use and disclosure, provide examples of acceptable/unacceptable practices, clarify their impact on assessment, and communicate the consequences of violations.

4.3. Students: use GenAI responsibly; critically verify AI outputs; disclose AI contributions; comply with assessment and confidentiality requirements.

4.4. Academic Integrity Committee: provide consultation; review incidents; coordinate prevention of violations and reporting.

5 Application of GAIDeT in the Educational Process

- 1 **Principle of Transparency.** All written assignments, projects, and other tasks completed with the use of GenAI must include an AI contribution disclosure. The use of the GAIDeT taxonomy is recommended. This allows instructors and students to clearly document which tasks were delegated to AI, while emphasizing the full responsibility of the author of the work (for details on GAIDeT: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2544331>).
- 2 **Content of the Disclosure.** The disclosure must indicate:
 - the AI tool(s) used (name, version);
 - the specific tasks delegated to AI;
 - confirmation of the author's full responsibility for the final result.
- 3 **Placement of the Disclosure.** The disclosure must be included at the end of the work (e.g., before or after the reference list) or in a designated section of the assignment. For oral presentations or project defenses, a brief oral statement or slide disclosure is acceptable.
- 4 **Declaration Generator.** To simplify the preparation of disclosures, the University recommends using the online GAIDeT Declaration Generator (<https://github.com/panbibliotekar/gaidet-declaration>), available:
 - in Ukrainian <https://panbibliotekar.github.io/gaidet-declaration/index-uk.html>
 - in English <https://panbibliotekar.github.io/gaidet-declaration/index>
- 5 **Citation of Source.** When using the online generator and disclosing GenAI contributions, it is recommended to cite the original source:

Suchikova, Y., Tsybuliak, N., & Teixeira da Silva, J. A. & Nazarovets, S. (2025). GAIDeT (Generative AI Delegation Taxonomy): A taxonomy for humans to delegate tasks to generative artificial intelligence in scientific research and publishing. *Accountability in Research*, in press. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08989621.2025.2544331>

6 Assessment and Validity

6.1. Classification of Work.

a) Controlled assessments (exams, in-class tests, practicums, defenses) – GenAI use may be prohibited, and tasks must be completed in a controlled environment.

b) Uncontrolled assignments (homework, projects, essays) – GenAI is permitted responsibly, with mandatory disclosure.

6.2. Assignment Design. Instructors should design tasks acknowledging the existence of GenAI (originality, course-specific context, intermediate artifacts, oral components, reflections, work logs).

6.3. AI Detectors. Automated GenAI “detectors” cannot serve as the sole basis for conclusions about academic misconduct; multiple indicators and a proper review procedure are required.

6.4. Suspected Violations. Cases are reviewed according to the Academic Integrity Code (right to explanation, transparent standard of evidence).

6.5. Assistive Technologies. For students with special educational needs (SEN), GenAI-based accommodations are permitted under University procedures; this must be specified in the assessment conditions.

7 Data, Confidentiality, and Intellectual Property

7.1. Confidential Data. It is prohibited to input students’ personal data, restricted materials/exam questions, official information, or commercially sensitive data into GenAI services.

7.2. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR). Copyright of student work and teaching materials must be respected; the use of GenAI does not alter authorship. Instructors must inform students of licensing terms for their work (separate consent may be required, if applicable).

8 Competencies and Training (AI Literacy)

8.1. Minimum Learning Outcomes for Students. Students must demonstrate:

- (i) understanding of GenAI capabilities and limitations;
- (ii) ability to critically verify outputs and references;

(iii) knowledge of ethical and legal foundations (transparency, citation/disclosure, confidentiality);

(iv) basic skills in integrating GenAI into their learning process.

8.2. Faculty Development. Regular training and consultations are provided for instructors on assignment design, assessment, confidentiality, and the use of the GAIDeT taxonomy.

8.3. Integration into Educational Programs. Program quality assurance teams gradually integrate AI literacy components into curricula (courses/modules).

9 Risk Management and Incident Handling

9.1. Common Risks

9.1.1. Hallucinations and fabricated references. GenAI may generate unreliable facts or sources.

9.1.2. Algorithmic bias. GenAI outputs may reproduce bias, leading to unequal or inaccurate representation of information.

9.1.3. Misattribution of authorship. Student work may contain significant AI-generated content without proper disclosure.

9.1.4. Data leakage. Using public online services without appropriate agreements/guarantees poses risks to personal, confidential, or exam-related data.

9.1.5. Intellectual property violations. GenAI use may lead to improper reproduction or modification of protected materials.

9.1.6. Overreliance on AI detectors. Detection tools are unreliable and cannot be the sole evidence of academic misconduct.

9.1.7. Excessive dependence on automation. Overuse of AI tools may reduce learning quality and hinder the development of core competencies.

9.2. Mitigation Measures

9.2.1. Design assignments that discourage misconduct and foster independent work.

9.2.2. Provide systematic training for students and faculty on responsible AI use and its limitations.

9.2.3. Use transparent AI-use disclosures in written work to ensure accountability and reproducibility.

9.2.4. For sensitive data, use only University-approved tools that guarantee appropriate protection.

9.2.5. In high-stakes assessments, use controlled environments that prevent unauthorized AI use.

9.3. Incident Reporting

9.3.1. Any participant in the educational process has the right to report suspected or actual violations related to AI use through designated University channels.

9.3.2. All reports are handled in accordance with principles of impartiality, confidentiality, and the right to explanation.

9.4. Sanctions

9.4.1. Confirmed violations are addressed in line with the University's Academic Integrity Code and relevant internal regulations.

9.4.2. Sanctions must be proportionate to the nature and severity of the violation and may range from warnings to disciplinary measures established by University rules.